

OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE AND CHANGES IN MENTAL STATUS IN PATIENTS WITH COVID-19

Nurilloeva Shahodat Nurillo qizi

Bukhara State Medical Institute named after Abu Ali ibn Sina

Assistant of the Department of Internal Medicine and Endocrinology

shakhodatnurilloeva92@gmail.com

Annotation: To study the features of the clinical course and modern diagnostic of arterial hypertension in the comorbidity of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) in patients at risk of developing cardiovascular complications in the disease with COVID-19.

Key words: Covid-19, arterial hypertension, electrocardiography, six-minute walk test, Heart-Vascular System, coronavirus, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

Research materials and methods: The research work was carried out in 2020 and 2021 in specialized departments of the COVID-19 Control Center in Bukhara, in a hospital setting, in patients with COVID-19.

The results obtained as a result of the analysis: The analysis confirms that patients who have undergone progressive COVID-19 based on Hypertension and have clinically recovered have a long-term effect on the clinical state of infection. After the prescribed treatment procedures, the quality-of-life index of the control group ranged from $35,2 \pm 0,6$ to $25,2 \pm 1,2$ points in patients with Hypertension II and from $45,1 \pm 1,6$ to $30,1 \pm 1,5$ points in patients with psychogenic changes.

Conclusions: in all countries of the Globe, with the advent of the COVID-19 pandemic, millions of people around the world are infected with it, spreading with great speed. Naturally, this situation is the main task of all researchers in the structure of the day in all aspects and in-depth study of this disease.

Relevance of the topic: In all countries of the world, the COVID-19 pandemic is spreading at a high speed, and millions of people around the world are

infected with it. Naturally, this situation makes a comprehensive and detailed study of this disease the main task of the day for all researchers. According to the current observations of world scientists, the process in some cases is asymptomatic, in most cases it is manifested by symptoms of an acute respiratory infection of the upper respiratory tract [2; 4; 5].

After that, some of the patients develop severe, acute respiratory distress syndrome, sepsis, resulting in failure of all organs (polyorgan) [1; 3; 6; 7; 8]. Today, it is recognized by all researchers that the disease of COVID-19 is more severe and causes more death in older people and patients with various co-morbidities.

Among them, special attention has been paid to the comorbid development of COVID-19 on the basis of cardiovascular diseases, but until now no final conclusion has been reached about the various diseases of the myocardium caused by COVID-19 [9; 11; 13; 15; 17; 18; 19; 20;].

Early diagnosis of these conditions, effective treatment and creation of principles of prevention are considered to be urgent problems of medicine. In all countries of the world, the disease of COVID-19 is currently developing rapidly in the form of a pandemic, and millions of people on earth are infected with this disease. Naturally, this process makes it their main task for all researchers to thoroughly study this disease [10; 12; 14; 16].

The purpose of the work: to study the specificity and modern diagnostic features of the combined clinical course of arterial hypertension and comorbid chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) in patients with a risk of developing cardiovascular complications in the course of COVID-19.

Research materials and methods: The study was carried out in 2020 and 2021 in the departments of the Bukhur city specialized center for fighting against COVID-19, treated in hospital conditions, patients with mental changes of COVID-19 and patients without mental changes of COVID-19 and "clinically recovered" was carried out.

In order to solve the tasks set before us, the scientific research work was carried out as follows. The study was conducted in patients with COVID-19 who had mental changes. The patients in the study had mental changes.

were divided into control groups with and without COVID-19. The study consisted of 94 patients, their age is 63.2 ± 1.2 . 54 (60%) of them were men and 40 (40%) were women.

58 (45%) of patients in this group had mental change II, 36 (55%) had mental change III. Group B consisted of 91 patients with mental illness who did not have COVID-19 and were recommended standard treatments (APFi or β -blockers), their mean age was 64.1 ± 1.2 years. 51 (56%) of them were men and 40 (44%) were women. 47.5% of patients in this group had mental change II, 52.5% had mental change III.

The clinical examination was conducted based on the following criteria and included: the patient's complaint and life history together with the duration and risk factors of mental changes, as well as comorbidities, physical examination, anthropometric parameters, objective examination, lung and heart auscultation, and abdominal palpation. .

Analysis of the obtained results: In our study, when the quality of life index of the patients was evaluated, the control group was equal to 35.2 ± 0.6 points in the II FS, and 45.1 ± 1.6 points in the III FS. These indicators in the II FS and III FS patients of the main A group were 9.6% and 13.1% more reliable than the control group patients, respectively, and averaged 39.7 ± 1.1 and 56.3 ± 1.1 points.

Quality of life indicators in the main group B patients were 4.8% and 17.3% higher than the control group and were 34.8 ± 1.7 and 54.2 ± 1.5 points.

Pre- and post-treatment dynamics (in points) of the clinical status assessment scale of patients with and without COVID-19 on the basis of mental change.

Analyzes confirm that patients who have developed COVID-19 on the basis of mental changes and who have recovered clinically have long-term effects of the infection on their clinical condition. The quality of life index after the treatment was

35.2 ± 0.6 to 25.2 ± 1.2 points in patients with II mental change, and 45.1 ± 1.6 to 30.1 ± 1.5 points in patients with III mental change. was equal. In group A, mental change in II patients reliably decreased from 39.7±1.1 to 26.8±0.4 points, and in III FS patients from 56.3±1.1 to 34.6±1.7 points. It reliably decreased from 34.8±1.7 to 33.2±0.3 points in patients with II mental change in group B, and from 54.2±1.5 to 46.2±1.6 points in patients with III mental change.

Such a research method is considered to be the simplest, most effective, and at the same time the most common method of assessing the work capacity of all patients with mental changes and chronic heart failure (CHF). For inspection, a 50-meter corridor of the medical institution where patients were treated was selected and carried out in that corridor. Patients were asked to walk along a corridor for 6 minutes. After that, the distance traveled by the patients was measured in meters. Care was taken to select the walking speed for all patients, that is, it was chosen so that even after the test, the patients should be able to continue moving without panting, feeling of heaviness in the legs and fatigue.

Conclusion: In all countries of the world, the COVID-19 pandemic is spreading rapidly and millions of people around the world are infected with it. Naturally, this situation makes a comprehensive and detailed study of this disease the main task of the day for all researchers. According to the current observations of world scientists, the process is sometimes asymptomatic, but in many cases it is manifested by symptoms of an acute respiratory infection of the upper respiratory tract [13].

After that, some of the patients develop severe, acute respiratory distress syndrome, sepsis, and finally, failure of all organs [polyorgan] occurs. Among the population, "Study of the onset, clinical characteristics and course of mental changes with the risk of cardiovascular complications in Covid-19 disease will allow timely identification and elimination of risk factors and comorbid conditions of hypertension, the establishment of established treatment procedures will provide

effective results in a short period of time and reduce the cost of expensive examinations. does not require.

Individual selection of treatment procedures according to the program and recommendations serves to prevent complications observed in patients and increase the effectiveness of treatment.

REFERENCES:

1. Nurilloeva S. N. PREVENTION OF OBESITY AND OVERWEIGHT IN PATIENTS WITH VARIOUS DEGREES OF HYPERGLYCEMIA //INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 7. – С. 74-81.

2. Nurilloeva Sh.N., Juraeva Kh.I. Adequacy pharmacotherapy of metabolic syndrome. // World journal of pharmaceutical research. August-Sept. - 2020. Volume 9. Issue 12. – P. 48 - 53.

3. Орзиев З. М., Нуриллова Ш. Н. Компетентность количественных показателей ведущих клинических признаков холестаза в дифференциации его градаций //Биология и интегративная медицина. – 2018. – №. 4. – С. 62-73.

4. Nurillokizi N. S. Metabolic Syndrome: Methods of Prevention and Treatment //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 475-482.

5. Nurilloeva Shakhodat Nurillo kizi. Diagnosis of Tubuloglomerular Relationship in Patients with Metabolic Syndrome // Journal of advanced research and stability (JARS) Volume: 01 Issue: 06 | 2021 ISSN: 2181-2608. –P. 469-474

6. Нуриллова Ш. Н. Частота встречаемости избыточной массы тела и ожирения //При нарушении углеводного обмена Журнал гепатогастроэнтерологических исследований, 75-ой Международной научно-практической конференции студентов-медиков и молодых учёных № 02(1), 18 мая 2021, стр -403

7. Нуриллова Ш.Н., Бадритдинова М.Н., Турли хил тана вазнида гипергликемия ҳолатини баҳолаш усуллари Услугий тавсиянома – 2021

8. Нуриллоева Ш.Н., Бадритдинова М.Н., Кардиоваскуляр хавфи ошган беморлар учун ортикча тана вазни ва семизликни олдини олиш усули Услубий тавсиянома – 2021

9. Kizi N. S. N. Assessment of the methods of the state of hyperglycemia at different body masses //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 9. – С. 359-366.

10. Nurilloeva Sh.N. Diagnosis of tubuloglomerular feedback in patients with metabolic syndrome // World medicine journal. No 1 (1) 2021. –P. 651-655

11. Nurilloeva Shakhodat Nurillo kizi. The Distribution of Smoking as a Risking Factor in the Development of Metabolic Syndrome in Overweight Patients // Volume 7| April, 2022 ISSN: 2795-7624. –P. 86-89.

12. Нуриллоева Ш.Н. Гипергликемиянинг турли тоифаларида семизликнинг тарқалиши // «Тиббиётда янги кун» 3 (41) 2022., ISSN 2181-712X. EISSN 2181-2187. 172-175-бет.

13. Жураева Х. И., Очилова Д. А., Кудратова Д. Ш. Распространенность и выявляемость сахарного диабета среди женского населения //Биология и интегративная медицина. – 2016. – №. 2. – С. 80-87.

14. Жураева Х. И., Бадридинова Б. К., Кадыров Б. С. Распространенность и состояние лечения артериальной гипертензии по данным анкетирования //Биология и интегративная медицина. – 2017. – №. 3. – С. 78-85.

15. Жураева Х. И., Алимова Ш. А. Применение опросного метода в ранней диагностике стенокардии в качестве скринирующего теста при профилактических обследованиях населения //Биология и интегративная медицина. – 2017. – №. 6. – С. 14-22.

16. ZHURAEVA K. I. et al. PECULIARITIES OF THE COURSE OF JOINT SYNDROME IN PERSONS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS //Journal of Natural Remedies. – 2021. – Т. 22. – №. 1 (1). – С. 92-98.

17. ZHURAEVA K. I. et al. PECULIARITIES OF THE COURSE OF JOINT SYNDROME IN PERSONS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS //Journal of Natural Remedies. – 2021. – T. 22. – №. 1 (1). – С. 92-98.